

A PRAGMATIC INVESTIGATION OF SELECTED NEWSPAPER EDITORIALS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16848785>

Keywords:

Pragmatics, Newspaper Editorials, Discourse Analysis, Linguistic Choices, Media Discourse, Editorial Language

Abstract: *This paper examined a pragmatic investigation of editorials from three prominent Nigerian newspapers—The Nation, Nigerian Tribune, and The Guardian—published in April, May, and June 2018, focusing on economy, politics/governance, security, education, and corruption. Employing Jacob Mey’s Pragmeme theory (2001), it examines how linguistic resources are contextually deployed to influence societal discourse. The objectives are to identify editorial contexts, analyze linguistic choices, and appraise their pragmatic functions, such as informing, advising, condemning, and praising. Using purposive random sampling, editorials were selected from print editions sourced at Kenneth Dike Library, University of Ibadan. The analysis highlights pragmatic features like Shared Situational Knowledge (SSK), Shared Cultural Knowledge (SCK), and Reference (REF), revealing how language reflects socio-economic and political issues. Findings indicate that editorials use emotional appeals, rhetorical questions, and metaphors to persuade readers while cautiously critiquing government actions. Linguistic choices vary by newspaper due to differing editorial styles and biases, impacting meaning-making. The study underscores the media’s role in shaping public discourse, recommending further research into truth and modality in editorials and urging readers to critically engage with content to ensure responsible communication.*

INTRODUCTION

The role of the media in any progressive society cannot be overlooked. While the media exercises functions such as educating, informing and entertaining their audience through news reportage, it also contributes to decision-making in the society through the editorial. Thus, Yassa (1996:6) described an editorial as a statement of

the editor’s opinion. It is the means through which any newspaper organisation gives the position of the editorial board on issues of topical or national interest. According to Duyile (2005:63), “it is the opinion of a newspaper simply written for the understanding of the readers, leading them to take decisions on the issues being discussed.” In the same vein, Ate

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Advance Journal of Linguistics and Mass Communication

Adv. J. Lin. M. Com

Volume: 9; Issue: 04

July-August, 2025

ISSN: 5314-6414 (p);

5344-3692 (e)

Impact Factor: 5.37

Advance Scholars Publication

International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

(2008) sees it as an argument exhibiting the logical reasoning, using the thoughts of the proprietor, for the purpose of persuading the readers (audience) to either kick against or accept an idea, policy or action based on facts available. In agreement to the above, the notion that the editorial is purposive in nature cannot be denied.

In an article, “How to Write an Analysis on an Editorial”, Russell Robert states that newspaper editorials play an important role in democratic societies as they provide a public forum in which ideas, political issues and policies, and other topics can be discussed and debated. These ideas, policies and other related issues are usually those which generate public concern. Okoro and Agbo (2003:125) lend similar voice as they describe the editorial as “a critical evaluation, interpretation and presentation of significant, contemporary events in such a way as to inform, educate, entertain, and influence the reader.”

Without any doubt, a good editorial is the voice of the organisation, it is meant to influence public opinion, provoke critical thinking and sometimes, move people to action, and lend a voice to the ideology or the interest of the ownership. As a result, the use of words is often selectively intentional and sometimes political, depending on the context. Also, its focus is to inform, educate or persuade its readers on a particular issue and this is expected to be done based on facts. However, there is a proliferation of media organisations whereby we have a lot of

uncensored news publication outlets which expose readers to a lot of unverified pieces of information. Similar to this is the emergence of what is called citizen journalism which Lasica (2003) describes as “participatory journalism”. Yet, there are a number of positive roles which the media has played and still plays in the economic growth and development of any nation. It has through its Agenda Setting Theory explored the ability of the media to influence the mind of the people.

The foregoing requires considering the degree of dependency of the society on the media. There are many theories of communication all of which allow the mass media to play certain roles in the society. In Suresh (2003), some of these theories include Media Dependency Theory “developed by Ball-Rokeach and DeFluer”. This theory states that the audiences depend on the media information to meet needs and reach goals while social institutions and media systems interact with audiences through shared socio-cultural knowledge to create needs, interests and motives.

In addition, Suresh identifies Development Communication Theory which has become established because of the notion that no society can develop without communication. It is also important to mention his reference to Agenda Setting Theory which, as McCombs and Shaw (1972) assert in a study on the 1968 American presidential election, caused the correlation between the media and the ordering of public

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International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/Ajlmc/index>

priorities. Based on their study, it can be drawn that the media plays a crucial role in shaping political, social, and economic realities in any society.

However, this current research study is challenged as well by the power held by the media. Some of these media outlets have without caution promoted the bias of their proprietorship or the writer. The manner in which language is being used as the means of communication demands attention. This is not without agreeing to the notion that it is not really possible to achieve complete objectivity. Language, being the vital tool in editorial writing, is complex and dynamic. As a result, if not carefully used, it could be destructive. Hence, the quest to attempt a pragmatic investigation of selected editorials of some Nigerian newspapers.

Meanwhile, language use in editorial writing is different from that of news writing or opinion articles. As earlier noted, an editorial is meant to influence, provoke and sometimes move people to action, hence the distinguishing use of linguistic resources. According to Suresh (2003), the experiences which readers gain from the media have immeasurable effects. In his study, he captured it under one of the Stalagmite theories called Meaning Theory. This theory focuses on how media experiences set meaning towards a particular direction. In the words of Suresh (2003), this is done by putting things in a particular framework. As a result, what is said with words, how it is said and the context of

language usage should be investigated. This then leads to considering what is known as pragmatics.

According to Yule (1996), pragmatics involves the interpretation of what is meant in a particular context and how the context influences what is said. By context, what it requires is a consideration for who the reader is, what the issue is, and when and where the communication takes place. Mey (2001) defines it as the study of the way human beings use their language in communication, based on a study of premises and how they bring about language use. Mey (2001:203) also asserts that, “pragmatics studies language as it is used by people, for their own purposes and within their own respective limitations and affordances”. This explains that choice of language use is influenced by factors such as context of social interaction, experience and intention, among others. Even though context is not constant, it is always at the centre of every pragmatic act. It is important to comprehending pragmatics. According to Mey (2001:36), “Context is a dynamic and not a static concept. It is understood as the continually changing surroundings that enable participants to interact and in which the linguistic expressions of their interactions become intelligible.” Based on the context, the linguistic resources have certain effects on participants as they are either encouraged to commit to a cause or to take an action. These effects also fall within

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the roles of the mass media such as educating, informing and persuading.

In the light of this, this study investigates the pragmatic acts in the editorials of *The Nation*, *Nigerian Tribune* and *The Guardian*. This research will enable us to identify how context influences linguistic choices and meaning. Attention will be paid to pragmatic functions established by the use of language in the selected editorials.

Statement of the Problem

A lot of studies which include pragmatics of political speeches and pragma-stylistic analysis of literary and non-literary texts have been carried out. In respect to editorials in newspapers, Okoro and Odoemelam (2013) attempt an analysis of editorial discourse on environmental challenges using the 2012 flooding in Nigeria as a case study. Similarly, Awan and Harun (2015) attempt a critical analysis of newspaper editorial discourse of the uprising in Libya and Syria. The duo use this to establish the relationship between the editorial and the uprising through making sense of meaning constructed in the mind of the readers. In the same vein, Lawal (2015) presents a pragmatics of truth and modality in newspaper editorials citing an example of *Punch* and *Nigerian Tribune*. In another contribution to the field of pragmatic study, Agu (2017) carries out an analysis of leadership selected cartoons in selected Nigerian dailies to evaluate the underlying meaning as intended by the author.

Her study draws attention to the need to examine the function of cartoons apart from entertainment.

On the contrary, some studies like Opubor (2012) attempts to establish the relationship between media and war. Using the Rwanda example, the study submits that the media also contribute to violence and genocide. Speaking on the same Rwanda war, Carver (2004) says much of the responsibility for the genocide in Rwanda can be blamed on the media. Yet, we cannot ignore the need for a tool that serves the society's need for critical evaluation of the activities of the government. However, enough attention has not been given to how the mass media through the editorials –the only medium through which they are expected to be objective, carry out, among other functions, their agenda-setting and development communication roles. As noted earlier, these roles with their powers have in one way or the other persuaded the reading public towards a particular position whether positive or negative. The pattern of debate and linguistic pattern in editorials need to be examined to show if developmental roles are being carried out objectively. Some of these roles include promoting economic progress, encouraging national culture, languages and unity of the country. Therefore, this study investigates selected editorials of Nigerian newspapers using *The Nation*, *Nigerian Tribune* and *The Guardian*.

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Aim and Objectives

This study aims at investigating how linguistic resources have been contextually employed to influence the society in the selected editorials of *The Nation*, *Nigerian Tribune* and *The Guardian*. The objectives of the study are:

1. To identify the contexts of selected editorials,
2. To investigate the choice of linguistic resources in the selected editorials, and;
3. To appraise the pragmatic functions established by the use of language in the selected editorials.

Research questions

For this study, the following research questions are expected to guide the researcher in the analysis of data. At the end of the study, answers are expected to be provided for the questions below.

1. What are the contexts of the selected editorials of Nigeria's national newspapers?
2. What linguistic resources are used in the selected editorials?
3. What pragmatic functions do the linguistic choices carry out?

Methodology

This research investigates selected editorials from three widely read Nigerian newspapers—*The Nation*, *Nigerian Tribune*, and *The Guardian*—published by Vintage Press Limited, African Newspapers of Nigeria Limited, and Guardian Media Group, respectively. These newspapers serve as vital communication links

between the government and the citizens and were selected using purposive random sampling due to their consistent focus on national issues. The study targets editorials published in April, May, and June 2018, addressing five critical categories: economy, politics/governance, security, education, and corruption—each of which generated public discourse and impacted societal well-being during that period. Under each category, one editorial per newspaper was selected using headlines and leads as clues. For the economy, editorials include *Don't kill a golden goose* (*The Nation*), *IMF on Nigeria's debt profile* (*Nigerian Tribune*), and *2018 Budget: Matters Arising* (*The Guardian*). Politics/governance features include *Buhari at three*, *APC congress and the threat to peace*, and *June 12 as day of National atonement*. Security-focused pieces are *Benue Killings*, *Danjuma's outburst*, and *The killings must stop*. On education, editorials include *History restored*, *Unfit teachers: Kaduna's example*, and *ASUU, government and the cycle of irresponsibility*. For corruption, selected titles are *More convictions, please*, *FG's plan to disburse \$322 million Abacha loot*, and *On the fight against money laundering*. All editorials were sourced from the reference section of Kenneth Dike Library, University of Ibadan. Despite the newspapers having online versions, the reliability and availability of the print editions influenced the researcher's preference. The selected editorials are analyzed using Jacob

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contextual ground of VCE, the editorial condemns the action of the government. The pragmatic act of condemning is enabled by the choice of words like “incongruous” and “perverse”. In the excerpt below, the editorial

Excerpt 2

The question then would be why any government would seek to slaughter a goose that lays golden eggs? According to RMAFC, there are several options open to the Federal Government other than outright sale of what is considered a most lucrative business. (*The Nation*, 4 April, 2018)

This speech act in this excerpt is expressive and declarative. The first sentence, although in the form of a question, expresses the opinion of the editorial concerning what the decision of the FG means. That is, “...to slaughter a goose that lays golden eggs”. Also, it rides on the shoulder of assumed shared socio-cultural knowledge (SSCK) as it uses metaphor (MPH) to present the value of NLNG to the economic posterity of Nigeria by comparing it to “a goose that lays golden eggs”. On the other hand, the second sentence is an indirect speech act in which the editorial appeals to authority, RMAFC, and declares that there are other options open to the FG. In addition, referring to the relevant authority - RMAFC, helps to establish the attention which the editorial intends to draw to the discourse issue without appearing biased or subjective. In sentence two, the pragmatic function of informing is also found. Furthermore, the study discovers a declarative speech act in the excerpt below. The contextual

engages the intended action of the government through questioning and reference to authorial statement. The contextual grounds and practs are considered.

grounds which help to achieve the pract of informing and commanding are shown below.

Context of politics/governance

Over the years, politics in Nigeria has been mostly a problem rather than a solution. It has become a field of selfish power-wielding where those in power want to perpetuate their stay at the expense of the pains and struggles of the electorates. Governance on the other hand is an act of governing. Even though both are separate, the situation of things in a supposedly democratic Nigerian system makes governance look like a cup of water in a desert; the impact even when felt is quickly overwhelmed by the ills and vices of politics. The common situation during electioneering periods is to feed the electorates with mouth-watering manifestoes during campaigns but upon resumption to office, their inactions hurt the electorates like that of a mother whose child is yet to walk at three.

In this context, different cases of unwholesome politicking, unaccountability, and power tussle were examined. The excerpts appraise the

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progress recorded by the Buhari/APC-led government in its three years, congresses and threat to peace and the declaration of June 12 as Democracy Day. The contextual grounds of SSK, REF, SCK, REL, among others, are explored to pract reminding, acknowledging, condemning and praising.

Excerpt 10

When the Muhammadu Buhari administration was inaugurated on May 29, 2015, expectations were high that fundamental changes had come. During the campaign, the new president and his party, the All Progressive Congress (APC) had told Nigerians that an end had come to their sufferings, and the country was about being launched into the orbit of great nations (*The Nation*, 29 May, 2018).

In the excerpt above, the expressive speech act explores the emergence of President Muhammadu Buhari. In the first sentence, “the Muhammadu Buhari” contextualizes a shared situational knowledge (SSK) about who the subject is as well as his importance. More importantly, this excerpt rides on referring to the things which had happened during Buhari’s campaign in 2015 to achieve REF and REL in the textual part. The use of “new” even though Buhari has always been in the political sphere for a long time is another subtle way in which the editorial gives voice to the good governance

Excerpt 4

In the past 36 months, there has been some progress recorded- in agriculture, physical infrastructure development, electricity generation and transmission, as well as social welfare (*The Nation*, 29 May, 2018).

In excerpt 3, the author lays background information concerning the emergence of President Buhari in 2015. The contextual grounds of REF and SSK which enable the pract of reminding are considered below.

which was expected of Buhari by the masses and not the usual clueless political gimmicks. Also, it is an indirect speech act which through its reference to the past, subtly draws the attention of Buhari’s administration to the many unrealized promises after three years in office. Linguistic choices such as “inaugurated”, “campaign”, “party” and “administration” establish the situational context of the editorial and pract reminding. In the following, there is a recall of activities in the past months. The contextual ground of SSK helps to pract of acknowledging.

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This is a declarative speech act which identifies with the successes of the government. Based on shared situational knowledge (SSK) about what used to obtain in the sectors mentioned in the excerpt, it could be inferred (INF) that indeed, the Buhari administration has made some progress. While it may not be intended, this practice which acknowledges the success of the Buhari administration serves as a reinforcement of interest and hope in the mind of the readers about the government. The acknowledgement is a psychological act as it appeals to the emotion of the readers.

Context of security

Security deals with the protection of lives and property within the territory of any nation. In this postmodern society, human beings have become exposed to a lot of threats to their lives and property and as a Nigerian situation teaches, every man needs to begin to find a way to protect his own self. Nigeria, over the past few years, has been experiencing eerie occurrences of killings, ravaging and destructive implosions. Theft,

Excerpt 5

It is curious that these herdsmen are able to strike at will, achieve their nefarious objectives and get away practically every time without being apprehended despite heavy military presence in and around Benue State (*The Nation*, 27 April, 2018).

This is an expressive speech act. Words such as “herdsmen”, “strike”, “nefarious”, “apprehended” and “military” suggest the prevalence of crime and insecurity while the linguistic choice of “curious” emphasises the

ritual activities, kidnapping, ethnic clashes, rape and mass murder have become the normal part of news feed. The results of these include displacement of people from their homes and hindrance to production activities. As a result of these challenges and the seeming incapability of the Nigerian security forces to handle them, widespread outcry emanates daily. Since insecurity of lives and property is another enemy to our economic growth and development, will a foreign investor set-up a business in a country which cannot protect its own?

In discussing issues related to security, the contextual grounds of SSK, INF, REF, and VCE are found in excerpts 5, 6 and 7. Largely, they perform the pragmatic function of condemning, indicting and conscientising the Federal Government having failed to curb the security challenges in Benue state. The choice of words establishes the attitude of the editorial towards the inhumane act of the herdsmen.

absurdity of the inability of the Federal Government to apprehend “these herdsmen”. On the other hand, from “these herdsmen”, it could be inferred (INF) that the perpetrators are known or it could just be a mere sense of

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identification since they have become a popular threat to lives and property in Nigeria. Similarly, it suggests a manner of addressing someone one has contempt for which could be true due to the inhuman activities of the herdsmen. On the textual part, the manner of reference (REF) to the herdsmen is based on an assumed shared situational knowledge (SSK) about the activities of the herdsmen across some states in the country. Also, “...despite heavy military presence” infers (INF) that there is a deliberate

Excerpt 6

The responsibility for the degeneration of the security situation in Benue State rests squarely with the Federal Government, which has clearly not responded to the terrorist activities of the Fulani herdsmen with the same decisiveness and seriousness it demonstrated as regards insurgent groups in the North-East, South-East or South-South (*The Nation*, 27 April, 2018).

Here, the expressive speech act is used to indict the FG. The excerpt employs the context of REF, VCE and SSK, to draw attention to the imbalance in the handling of security challenges by the FG. Occasions when the government acted in respect to insurgencies were recalled (REF) while faulting the disregard for the need to curb the killings in Benue State and others. Words such as “responsibility”, “degeneration”, “terrorist activities”, “decisiveness” and “seriousness” contextualize the attitude (VCE) of the

Excerpt 7

We find it difficult to comprehend why President Buhari remains hesitant to change the current service chiefs, whose tenure he extended twice ostensibly for meritorious performance (*The Nation*, 27 April, 2018).

failure on the part of the FG. Therefore, the practice of conscientising the government and the masses is found.

Similarly, the excerpt below performs the pragmatic function of indicting the government and conscientising the masses. Based on the contextual ground of REF, VCE and SSK, it accuses the government of failing to perform its constitutional exclusive duty of ensuring security of lives and property.

newspaper to the prevailing atmosphere in Benue State. Also, the reference, “...as regards insurgent groups in the North-East, South-East, or South-South” infers (INF) that the FG is partial. Also, it practices conscientising the masses and suggests that the failure of the FG to act is deliberate as a result of connivance between the armed forces and the herdsmen. In the same vein, the following condemns the complacency of the government and informs the masses.

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This is an expressive speech act. Expressively, the excerpt points to the subtle means by which media organisations exercise their roles as watchdogs. Though not directly done, but the pattern of linguistic choices achieves the pragmatic function of condemning the inability of the president to act as and when due. Based on inference (INF), this excerpt implies that the lack of appropriate leadership in security agencies has brought about the inability to resolve the bloodbath in states like Benue. Armed with the linguistic choice of “hesitant”, the reference (REF) to the extension of the tenure of the service chiefs in the light of recent breach of security, infers (INF) that the service chiefs have overstayed their welcome. Achieving meaning has also been possible here based on shared situational knowledge (SSK) about the various killings in some parts of the country and the indecisiveness with which the situation is being managed by the FG.

Findings

Based on the study, some specific findings were made. They are discussed below.

The art of persuasion through words has also crept into the media due to the need to retain readership. In order to make readers embrace their perspectives, it was discovered that all the selected newspaper editorials employed the use of emotional appeal in the manner that suits their in-house styles. Techniques which include rhetorical questions and conscientising were used to make the readers reflect on the discourse.

Also, while there are two fundamental roles of the media: informing and educating, the editorials in this research employed varying pragmatic functions. They include conscientising, condemning, indicting, encouraging, and advising to achieve individual goals. In the same vein, the study shows that, due to authors’ different world-views and the owners of the selected newspapers’ biases, issues were engaged from different perspectives. As a result, multiple uses of acts were discovered in most of the selected excerpts. In addition, choice of words made reveals that editorial decisions are widely dependent on in-house style and not conventional rules.

The study also revealed that all the newspapers have a connection in using metaphors to indirectly make assertions and pract condemnation. They engaged in accusing and indicting through the tools of presupposition and inference. However, different layers of meaning were commonly presented to the readers. The consequence of this is that without necessary shared knowledge of the situation as well as cultural beliefs, the readers are bound to misinterpret contents of the editorial and may take damaging actions.

Meanwhile, in their attempt to draw attention to germane issues, the authors made careful efforts not to proclaim themselves as authorities. In fact, in order to avoid reports that are likely to be refuted as libellous, words like “claimed” and “alleged” were employed.

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It was also noted that issues within the five contexts were not engaged in equal manners. Obviously, newspaper authors simply choose to write on what appeals to the editorial board among the myriads of issues that break daily. This made it quite impossible for the study to adequately establish common grounds among them.

Conclusion

The analysis revealed that newspaper editorials, while fulfilling their developmental roles, carefully select linguistic expressions that reflect the context of discourse and subtly convey their perspectives without overtly confronting authority. In addressing sensitive issues like bloodbaths, most editorials implicitly criticized the government, using cautious language to avoid drawing undue attention. For other topics such as the economy, security, education, and governance, the editorials employed linguistic tools to warn, advise, inform, and acknowledge. Questions were used as psychological devices to engage readers and position them as active decision-makers, while also protecting the newspapers from repercussions. The strategic use of pronouns like “we” fostered reader involvement, and words like “claimed” or “alleged” signaled uncertainty or skepticism. Through illocutionary acts, the editorials asserted opinions, passed judgments, and gave recommendations—frequently using “must” to

express urgency and necessity, while “should” served as a softer directive toward solutions. This reflects a balance between responsibility, influence, and caution in editorial communication.

Recommendations

The research study focused on the pragmatic investigation of selected Nigerian newspapers editorials in April, May and June, 2018. Based on the study, the researcher presents the following recommendations which will be useful for further study in the field of pragmatics and media communications. The recommendations are:

1. This study only focused on the pragmatic investigation of editorials. Further research should look critically into the pragmatics of truth and modality in editorials. This will reveal how editorials use words to point out what is supposed to be true rather than using words like “alleged” and “claimed”.
2. Newspaper readers should learn to pay careful attention to editorial contents before acting upon them. Direct or indirect submissions should be interrogated and doing so will make authors mind what is said and how it is said.
3. Certain attitudes are displayed through words, so editorial content should be mindful of choices made. By so doing, the attitude of readers will be influenced correctly toward developmental issues.

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4. Authors should uphold national interest above readership. This will promote the objectivity and credibility of newspapers.
5. Rather than focusing excessively on in-house style, editorials should embrace general principles of linguistic choices. In this respect, establishing an effective regulatory board will guide the linguistic choices made in editorial.

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<https://www.definitions.net/definition/metapragmatics>

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